

IRISCC

D6.2

Analysis report of D4Science VRE fitness for purpose and adaptations required

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Abstract

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This Deliverable D6.2 demonstrates the benefits using the framework of D4Science for the IRISCC Demonstrators. It elaborates a roadmap to onboard and host the IRISCC Demonstrators. The IRISCC Project will develop and integrate a wide range of tools and resources, enabling researchers to effectively manage, analyse, and visualise climate data. The public Deliverables D6.2 and D4.1 (Report on the full Demonstrator design) together provide input for setting-up a series of joint IRISCC WP4-WP6 Workshops, starting on October 2024.

Overall, D6.2 has delivered a valuable resource for the IRISCC demonstrator development. Based on the framework of D4science. The resulting Virtual Research Environment (VRE) will continue to evolve and expand its capabilities to meet the evolving needs of researchers and policymakers even beyond the IRISCC Project, building upon the foundation established in this deliverable.

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Key Terminology / Acronyms	
Term/Acronym	Definition
AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Interface
AnaEE	ANAEE Infrastructure is a pan-European research infrastructure network focused on advancing ecosystem research.
ACTRIS	Aerosol, Clouds, and Trace gases Research infrastructure: A research infrastructure that focuses on the observation of aerosols, clouds, and trace gases.
CCP	The Cloud Computing Platform is a sophisticated system of distributed components encompassing different technological and operational domains.
DM	DM (Dataminer) is a powerful data management and analysis platform designed to support researchers in various scientific domains. It offers a comprehensive suite of tools for data acquisition, curation, integration, analysis, and visualization in the D4science VRE.
DNS	Domain Name System translates website addresses like www.IRISCC.eu to numerical IP addresses.
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud: An open science cloud that provides researchers in Europe with access to data, computing resources, and services.
EGI.eu	European Grid Initiative: An initiative that promotes the development and operation of a pan-European grid infrastructure.
EIRENE	European Infrastructure for Environmental Routine Observation Networks: A European infrastructure for routine environmental observations.
EMBRC	EMBRC (European Marine Biological Resource Centre) is a pan-European infrastructure network that provides access to a wide range of marine biological resources and associated services.
eLTER	eLTER (European Long-Term Ecosystem Research Infrastructure) is a pan-European network of research stations and facilities dedicated to long-term ecological research.

FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable: A set of principles for research data management that ensure data is easily discoverable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable.
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HTTP	HTTP (Hypertext Transfer Protocol) is the foundation of the World Wide Web, enabling the transfer of data between web servers and web browsers. It operates on a client-server model, where a client (typically a web browser) sends a request to a server, and the server responds with the requested data, such as a webpage, image, or video.
IAGOS	In-service Aircraft for Global Observing System: A global observing system that conducts measurements of trace gases and aerosols in the atmosphere.
ICOS	Integrated Carbon Observing System: An integrated system for observing the carbon cycle.
ICT	Information and Communication Technology. Here e.g. the adoption of Microservice development resulted in substantial improvements of interoperability and composability of software components even when these components are distributed across a network.
IRISCC	Integrated Research Infrastructure Services for Climate Change Risk. Horizon Europe funded project aiming to provide Integrated RI services for Climate Change risks.
MhM	Mosaic Hydrological Model: a complex model used for simulating hydrological processes at various scales, from local to continental.
REST API	Representational State Transfer (REST) Application programming interface (API).
RIS	European Research Infrastructures: Research infrastructures are facilities that are essential for conducting research.
SAI	Software and Algorithms Importer
SeaDataNet	SEADaNET is an international network of data centers dedicated to the long-term preservation and access of marine research data.
TSMP	Terrestrial System Modeling Platform: a framework that integrates various Earth system models, including those for land surface, atmosphere, ocean, and biosphere.

UI	A user interface (UI) is the graphical interface that enables users to interact with a computer or other electronic device.
VLab	The Blue-Cloud thematic Virtual Labs are the main test beds for users to get the hang of the Blue-Cloud framework.
VRE	Virtual Research Environment: A virtual environment that provides researchers with tools and resources for collaboration and conducting research projects.
WP	Work Package
WPS	WPS (Web Processing Service) is an OGC (Open Geospatial Consortium) standard for processing geospatial data on a remote server. WPS provides a flexible and interoperable framework for a wide range of geospatial applications, including data analysis, visualization, and modelling.

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Executive summary

IRISCC is a Horizon Europe project that aims to provide **Integrated Research Infrastructure Services for Climate Change risks**. Its goal is to foster cutting-edge research and evidence-based policymaking to improve Europe's resilience to climate change. The project focuses on developing **scientific and knowledge services** that leverage existing research infrastructures and data to address climate-related challenges. This includes areas such as extreme weather events, biodiversity loss, and food security. By combining data from various sources and providing advanced analytical tools, IRISCC aims to support climate change research and inform decision-making.

Work Package 6 of the IRISCC project aims to harmonise access procedures for research infrastructures and digital services and develop integrated services using the D4Science virtual research environment (VRE). This deliverable (D6.2) gives a short introduction to D4Science VRE and the IRISCC demonstrators as the basis for project decisions. It summarises the roadmap and planned use of the VRE for integrating demonstrator services and data.

D4Science VRE is a cutting-edge VRE designed to facilitate collaborative scientific research. It provides a centralised platform where researchers from diverse disciplines can share data, resources, and computational tools. By leveraging advanced technologies, D4Science enables seamless integration and interoperability of heterogeneous data sources, fostering new insights and discoveries.

The IRISCC Project will benefit of D4Science VRE by providing:

- **Centralised Platform:** Integrates various services and data for efficient research workflows.
- **Open Science Practices:** Promotes FAIR principles for data management and sharing.
- **Scalability and Flexibility:** Adapts to accommodate diverse research needs.
- **Enabling Collaboration and Knowledge Exchange:** Enables seamless collaboration among researchers.

Roadmap Development onboarding the IRISCC Demonstrators to the D4Science VRE:

- The deliverable provides a brief description of the IRISCC demonstrators.
- It outlines a roadmap for integrating these demonstrators' data and services into the D4Science VRE.
- The roadmap includes steps like initial meetings, workshops guiding technical discussions to ensure a smooth integration process.

Overall D6.2 sets the ground for starting the proposed roadmap to develop a unified platform using the framework of D4Science. Thus, the new VRE will serve as a valuable platform for the IRISCC project demonstrations, facilitating research integration, collaboration, and open science practices.

1. Objective of this report

The overall objective of IRISCC Work Package 6 (WP6) is to harmonise TA and VA access procedures for efficient access management and provision, as well as for positive user experience to access installations and digital services, and to deploy and provide the technical interoperability framework for integrated IRISCC services.

Task 6.3 is aimed at formulating and deploying a technical interoperability and FAIRness framework to support developments of integrated IRISCC services. In particular this task will analyse the adoption and possible expansion of the D4Science VRE (Virtual Research Environment) e-infrastructure functionalities managed by CNR-ISTI, to support the technical integration and development work on the Scientific and Knowledge services done in WP4 and WP5, as well as for supporting the later operation of these integrated services with computing and storage resources. Task 6.3 facilitates the work with Demonstrator and Science Design Lab (SDL) teams on assessing the existing functionalities and components, and possible adaptations, required for developing and operating proposed integrated services, and for achieving a high level of FAIRness. Configuring and launching the D4Science VRE as an interoperability framework for IRISCC and making adaptations, where needed and feasible. Further, Task 6.3 ensures the uptake of the VRE and provides technical support to IRISCC teams during service integration, including possibility of making connections to external services, such as for data and computing. From the experience gained with WP4 technical work (completed in Month 30), Task 6.3 will provide guidance documentation for WP5 co-creation activities to use the VRE as a 'virtual playground' in the co-design process in the latter part of the project (Months 30–54).

This Deliverable D6.2 gives an introduction to the VRE D4Science as well as a short description of the IRISCC WP4 Demonstrators. It will show the steps already taken and future steps needed to develop a roadmap onboarding IRISCC Demonstrator selected services and data to the D4Science Virtual Research Environment.

2. Introduction to the VRE D4Science: A Digital Infrastructure for Scientific Collaboration

VRE D4Science is a cutting-edge virtual research environment designed to facilitate collaborative scientific research. It provides a centralised platform where researchers from diverse disciplines can share data, resources, and computational tools. By leveraging advanced technologies, D4Science enables seamless integration and interoperability of heterogeneous data sources, fostering new insights and discoveries.

The central D4Science platform is operated by the Institute of Information Science and Technologies (ISTI) of the Italian National Research Council (CNR). CNR-ISTI is a leading research institute in Italy, specialising in information technology and telecommunications. They have been instrumental in developing and maintaining the D4Science VRE as a valuable resource for scientific collaboration.

The D4Science VRE stands out for its comprehensive data management capabilities, which form the foundation of its support for the entire research lifecycle. Researchers can securely upload, store, and manage their datasets within the platform, benefiting from robust access controls and high availability. The VRE integrates advanced tools for data analysis, modelling, and visualisation, enabling scientists to derive meaningful insights through customizable workflows. In addition, D4Science promotes seamless data sharing and collaboration, empowering researchers to co-develop projects and exchange knowledge in real time. From data collection and processing to analysis, and publication, D4Science VRE provides a unified environment that enhances research productivity and fosters scientific collaboration.

In addition, VRE D4Science provides a comprehensive suite of computational resources. These resources include Cloud Computing clusters, specialised software tools, and virtual laboratories. By leveraging these resources, researchers can conduct complex simulations, analyse large datasets, and develop innovative scientific models. D4Science also integrates with various external services, such as commercial cloud computing platforms (e.g. Google Cloud Platform) and scientific databases, expanding its capabilities and reach.

D4Science is committed to advancing Open Science and ensuring Research Reproducibility. By adhering to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and

Reusable), the platform ensures that research data and results are easily discoverable, accessible, and reusable by the wider scientific community. D4Science also promotes the development and use of open-source software tools and workflows, fostering collaboration and driving innovation across disciplines.

2.1 Key Components of VRE D4Science

The VRE D4Science workflow (see Figure 1) is designed to support a wide range of scientific research activities, from data collection and management to analysis and dissemination [R1]. The core components of the workflow include:

- **Data Ingestion:** Researchers upload their data into the VRE, either through direct upload or by integrating with external data sources.
- **Data Management:** The VRE provides tools for organising, storing, and managing data, including metadata management and data versioning.
- **Data Analysis:** Researchers can access a variety of computational tools and resources to analyse their data, such as statistical analysis, machine learning, and simulation software.
- **Data Visualization:** The VRE offers visualisation tools to help researchers explore and understand their data, including interactive plots, charts, and maps.
- **Collaboration and Sharing:** Researchers can collaborate with colleagues on projects, share data and results, and publish their findings through the VRE.

The VRE D4Science is built on a modular architecture that allows for flexibility and scalability. Corresponding to the workflow the key components of the VRE include:

- **Data Management Platform:** This component provides tools for data storage, retrieval, and management, including metadata management and data versioning.
- **Computational Resources:** The VRE offers a variety of computational resources, including high-performance computing clusters, virtual machines, and specialised software tools.
- **Visualisation Tools:** The VRE provides a range of visualisation tools to help researchers explore and understand their data.
- **Collaboration Tools:** The VRE includes tools for collaboration, such as project management, messaging, and file sharing.
- **Integration with External Services:** The VRE can integrate with external services, such as cloud storage platforms, scientific databases, and research infrastructures.

These components work together to support the VRE D4Science workflow, enabling researchers to efficiently manage, analyse, and share their data.

Figure 1. The D4Science VRE Workflow.

In the following paragraphs more details will be given on the D4Science VRE Common Services which encompass a wide range of functionalities, facilitating collaboration, data analytics, result publication, and seamless integration with external systems, and therefore play a pivotal role in promoting Open Science practices, enabling researchers to leverage the benefits of advanced e-infrastructures. The architecture and functionalities of D4Science will be illustrated with a description of the Blue-Cloud VRE, which has been set up with D4Science for the Blue-Cloud pilot project and which currently is operated and expanded for the Blue-Cloud 2026 project [R2]. For IRISCC a comparable instance of D4Science will be established to serve as IRISCC VRE e-infrastructure. The Blue-Cloud description in particular considers the analytical engines of the VRE.

2.2 Blue-Cloud VRE logical architecture and common services

Figure 2 illustrates the Blue-Cloud VRE Common Services logical architecture, with Blue-Cloud Virtual Laboratories that can be built and operated using the VRE functionalities. The VRE is built by exploiting the Virtual Machines operated and provisioned by D4Science, together with services for their management and administration (VRE federated resources). Above this layer, a number of services form the enabling framework, essential for supporting the operation of all services and VREs. Specifically, this framework includes:

1. Information System service: This service allows for the dynamical (de)registration and discovery of all VRE resources (data sources, services, computational nodes, etc.), by users and other services;
2. Identity and Access Management (IAM) service: Responsible for handling authentication and authorization services, as well as auditing services. It is capable of granting and tracking access and usage actions from users; and
3. VRE Management System service: This service facilitates the deployment of specialised Virtual Labs (VLabs) based on a selected subset of applications.

Figure 2. The Blue-Cloud VRE common services logical architecture.

On top of this layer, three frameworks, namely the Storage Framework, the Catalogue Framework and the Analytics Computing Framework are built to provide common facilities to users [R3], [R4], [R5].

The **Analytics Computing Framework**, to date, offers set of data analytical services that can be requested and customised in the VLabs:

- **Analytics engine:** This service features the following two engines.
 - DataMiner (DM): the engine that was used in Blue-Cloud and will be maintained in Blue-Cloud 2026. It comprises a rich array of ready to use analytical methods ranging from data clustering methods to geospatial data analytics, occurrence data management, and species distribution maps generation.
 - Cloud Computing Platform (CCP): a newer engine sharing the same design principles and main features as the DataMiner. CCP is being evolved in Blue-Cloud 2026, to enhance its functionality by leveraging on the most recent advancements in IT and software engineering.
- **RStudio:** This service allows users to perform online statistical analyses. It offers a predefined list of R packages, and each VLab can define its RStudio server

configurations. The configurations include a Standard (4 cores/8GB RAM) and a Large (8 cores/32GB RAM) one.

- **JupyterLab:** a web-based interactive development environment designed for Jupyter notebooks, code, and data. It allows users to configure and arrange the user interface to support a wide range of workflows in data science, scientific computing, and machine learning.

The **Catalogue Framework** primary component is the VRE Data Catalogue. This service is built on open-source technology for data catalogues, CKAN (ckan.org). Through this Catalogue users can search and browse data, products, and resources (posters, deliverables, etc) of interest from the Blue-Cloud community.

The **Storage Framework** operates transparently to users and virtualises the available storage technologies and their actual physical hardware.

2.3 Analytics Computing Framework

The Analytics Computing Framework includes a set of services and components for performing data processing and mining on information sets. Section 2.3.1 is about the two available engines for importing and execution of analytical methods. The Cloud Computing Platform (CCP) is the newer engine that will evolve in Blue-Cloud 2026, and the DataMiner, the engine that was used in the previous Blue-Cloud project and it will be maintained but not evolved in Blue-Cloud 2026. While section 2.3.2 is about JupyterHub, used as the enabling platform for the RStudio application, which allows users to perform online statistical analyses and the JupyterLab¹ application, the web-based interactive development environment for Jupyter notebooks². Section 2.3.3 is about the support offered by the VRE for the deployment of ShinyApps³, via ShinyProxy and any other Containerised (Docker) applications.

2.3.1 Analytics Engines

2.3.1.1 Cloud Computing Platform (CCP)

Over the last decade, several fields of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) have experienced a major evolution and numerous advancements. One of the most noteworthy is the widespread adoption of Microservice development patterns. This resulted

¹ <https://readthedocs.org/projects/jupyterlab/>

² <https://jupyter-notebook.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

³Shiny Apps: An Interactive Guide to Developing Web Applications with R.
<https://github.com/rstudio/shiny>

in substantial improvements in terms of interoperability and composability of software components even when these components are distributed across a network.

REST APIs have become a fundamental technology to build Web Services, while Web components and Microfrontends aim to extend the advantages of service orientation directly into the Graphical User Interfaces (GUIs). The emergence of new programming languages with smaller footprint, improved domain specificity and simplified syntax, and their adoption has been boosted thanks to the increased freedom that aforementioned improvements allow.

As a result, the adoption of microservice and cloud-native approaches has led to the emergence of new requirements and novel patterns have emerged at the operational level as well. The so-called concept of “containerisation”, serving as the lightweight alternative to virtualisation of computing resources, has become the de facto standard for packaging and provisioning software. Tools and languages have been created for the automation of provisioning, microservice orchestration, inspection and monitoring of software and infrastructure components.

2.3.1.2 CCP Design principles and implementation

The vast landscape of new opportunities described above, in addition to the greatly increased requirements and expectations, represented the major drivers for the design and development of the CCP. This platform represents the result of a comprehensive re-evaluation of the existing DataMiner solution⁴. After a critical overview of the current solution DataMiner and its Software Importer (SAI), a use case driven analysis of the requirements for CCP has been performed.

The following use cases have been identified:

- Use case 0 – Workspace abstractions: CCP should be able to access file resources stored on different distributed workspace abstractions.
- Use case 1 – Access Data as a Service: CCP should be able to access data exposed as services.
- Use case 2 – Low-level polyglot: CCP should natively support as many programming and scripting languages as possible.
- Use case 3 – High-level polyglot: CCP should support different execution environments for scripts and applications.
- Use case 4 – Support complex tools: CCP should support complex tools that could have been used in pre-existing workflows.
- Use case 5 – Support coarse grained parallelism: CCP should support the possibility of subdividing scripts into parallel tasks.
- Use case 6 – Support fine grained parallelism: CCP should support the exploitation of parallel execution environments.
- Use case 7 – Link to structured code repositories: CCP should enable access to code stored on different code and artefact repositories.

⁴ <https://dev.d4science.org/>

- Use case 8 - Develop with non-headless workflows: CCP should support environments with their own visual or interactive frontend.
- Use case 9 - Discovery, consolidation, and community driven growth: It should be possible to discover consolidated data sources, methods and algorithms, both interactively and programmatically.

CCP is a sophisticated system of distributed components encompassing different technological and operational domains. This system includes a plethora of resources (hardware, virtual machines, databases and datastores) and processes such as orchestration logic, application and integration software developed on purpose or made available by the open-source community. At the bottom of these stacks lie the physical resources which can be anything from full-blown data centres to personal laptops. Each physical host can provide its own set of services including storage facilities, code repositories, databases and more. A special physical host is represented by the D4Science platform where the CCP core runs together with other core essential services. Most importantly, a physical host can provide a computing infrastructure which represents the set of computing resources used to run methods in executions performed on compatible runtimes.

A method is a lightweight data structure that describes an algorithm, procedure or function. This descriptor provides information about input parameters, expected output results, authorship and versioning. Most importantly, it defines the compatibility with one runtime and the affinity to one or more computing infrastructures. Method descriptors are all kept inside a dedicated method repository hosted by the D4Science data centre.

In order to be executable, a method has to be associated with a runtime which can be seen as a (Docker) container. This container is able to provide everything needed by the method including its operating system and application dependencies. Runtimes are complex and “large” artefacts that are kept in specialised runtime repositories. One such repository is hosted by the D4Science data centre but others can be provided among the services of a data centre. Additionally, access to public runtime repositories offered by third parties is also feasible.

The execution of a method is a complex process that involves the following macro phases:

- delivering a method descriptor and a compatible runtime to one of the affine infrastructures;
- bootstrapping the runtime and deploying the method;
- running the method by conveying the user provided inputs;
- monitoring the execution by forwarding real-time logs to the requesting user;
- uploading the generated; and
- cleaning up by destroying the dedicated runtime.

All the information recorded during the execution of a method is stored in a dedicated execution repository. The execution repository serves as a temporary storage that helps users track their executions. Upon completion, an execution can be archived, restored or resubmitted. These operations are coordinated by an internal piping and wiring network. In

order to participate as a computing infrastructure, a data centre has to provide a controller component that represents the infrastructure side termination of the wiring and piping. Users can interact with the CCP and its features in a way that hides away most of this complexity. This can be done either programmatically or by accessing simple widgets embedded in web pages or portals or more complex applications. This architectural vision translates to the logical architecture depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Logical architecture design.

The logical architecture in Figure 3 illustrates the natively distributed nature of CCP. Starting from the top, infrastructures are computing resources that will run CCP executions (shown as green Es). These infrastructures can be hosted in data centres. The term data centre actually encompasses everything ranging from simple laptops up to clusters of nodes. Nodes refer to machines such as servers or PCs delegated to run the actual execution of methods. A computing infrastructure can be connected to the CCP core by a Controller component. Controllers are processes that communicate via a dedicated API with the CCP in order to poll for tasks to perform on the Infrastructure they control. Tasks may include deploying new runtimes, provisioning and execution of methods, reporting on the overall status of the Infrastructure. In order to keep the current state for CCP, a repository of methods and executions is implemented. For methods, the descriptor data structures are kept in the proper repository.

For each execution, the repository stores a lot of information that allows for an exact reproduction of the execution:

- the method descriptor;
- the descriptor of the infrastructure that executed the method;
- the execution request with all input parameters;
- the standard output and error channels;
- all the data that is produced and uploaded by the method; and
- metadata identifying the user that requested the execution.

A repository for runtimes is provided in order to provide trusted and validated runtimes, with the flexibility to utilise external repositories or those provided by the data centre hosting infrastructures. All the components adhere to well-defined and where possible, standard-compliant REST APIs. This allows users to programmatically interact with CCP without having to know the complex architecture.

A set of widgets (as shown in Figure 4), such as “Method List”, “Method Form”, “Execution Form”, and “Execution Monitor” are delivered in the form of web components. These components can be embedded into web pages, portals or other web based complex applications such as Jupyterhub. Two core applications are provided in D4Science portals involved in Blue-Cloud by combining the available widgets: the “CCP Method Manager and Importer” and “CCP Method Execution Manager”. Given that many of the operations involved are lengthy and asynchronous, CCP includes a Logging Service that is used to send back real-time notifications to user components about the state of a particular process. These notifications include advancement of Executions, advertisement of Infrastructures status updates, and error conditions.

All complex processes involved in CCP are implemented as workflows inside a Workflow Orchestrator. This Orchestrator not only provides a high level of flexibility and customisation, but also allows for a centralised endpoint to monitor progress and check for errors that may occur. At the foundation of all interactions among external actors, such as users and Controllers, a strong authentication and authorisation mechanism is enforced by Identity and Access Management. This mechanism not only enables security requirements, rather it also implements ownership attribution and auditing.

Figure 5 depicts a detailed technical view of the CCP instance that is currently available in the Blue-Cloud VRE. CCP is packaged as a Docker stack that is deployed in the D4Science data centre at the CNR premises in Pisa. Access to the internal components either through APIs or Widgets is controlled by a Policy Enforcement Point (PEP) that authenticates and authorises every operation. Security enforcement is obtained in cooperation with the D4Science Identity and Access Management (IAM) service built with Keycloak.

Methods List

Method Form

Execution Form

Execution Monitor

Figure 4. Some examples of CCP UI Components (User Interface).

Harbor is used to implement the runtime repository, or container registry. Currently Docker is supported in production as the type of runtime. Controllers are deployed outside the CCP stack “in front of” the Computing infrastructure they control. Communication towards CCP is performed via authenticated HTTPs calls, in order to grant access from any point of the Web. In the current deployment there are two infrastructures available, one in a datacenter

in Pisa (CNR) the second one in Catania (GARR-CT). Two main applications have been provided for Blue-Cloud users (Method importer and Method runner) as a combination of the developed UI Components.

Figure 5. Detailed CCP architecture in Blue-Cloud VRE.

Figure 5 shows the Web User Interfaces of the CCP available in the Blue-Cloud VRE. Specifically:

- Method List example: List of the available methods. Searchable by name, description and keywords. Item is draggable to an Execution Form;
- A Method Form example: to specify a Method according to the OGC Process specification data model. Provide authorship and version information, naming, keywords, inputs, outputs and provisioning information;
- Execution Form example: to request the execution of a method by providing inputs. Allow for code generation in order to request an execution programmatically in languages such as Python, JPython for Jupyter, R, Julia; and
- Execution Monitor example: for the execution tracking with real time streaming of standard output and error logs produced by the method execution. Extra functionality like execution archiving, restoring or replay, code generation for programmatic resubmission of executions in common languages such as Python, JPython for Jupyter, R, Julia.

2.3.1.3 Data Miner

The DataMiner (DM) [R6] engine includes a set of services and components for performing data processing and mining on information sets. Analytical methods employed by users can be developed in almost any programming language (R, Java, Python, Fortran, Octave, etc.) and then imported via the Software and Algorithms Importer (SAI) and executed via the DataMiner engine. Once imported through SAI, DataMiner offers these scripts as a Service, handling aspects like multi-tenancy and simultaneous usage. This system also simplifies script updates for scientists, eliminating the need for extensive re-deployment processes. Essentially, SAI facilitates the creation of processes that operate on the Blue-Cloud VRE Cloud computing platform, accessible through the Web Processing Service (WBS) standard.

To import a script, one must follow three steps in SAI:

- Define the input, output, and types for the primary script that coordinates the process.
- Construct the Software: This step involves packaging the script and readying it for use on the computing platform. It's necessary whenever changes are made to the script's interface (inputs/outputs) or its dependencies.
- Deploy the Software: This final step allows the script to run on the computing platform within the virtual laboratory where it's been uploaded.

Moreover, there's a Repackage function, useful for updating an already published script that has undergone modifications without altering its inputs/outputs or dependencies.

Once imported, scripts become exploitable through the DataMiner component GUI which presents two panels (Figure 6):

- On the left panel, the GUI presents the list of computational methods available in the VLab, which are semantically categorised (the category is indicated through SAI). For each method, the interface calls the WPS DescribeProcess operation to get the descriptions of the inputs and outputs.
- On the right panel, the GUI presents a form allowing to specify the input parameters of the selected computational method. Input data can be selected from the Workspace clearly.

Figure 6. Blue-Cloud VRE Software and Algorithms Importer Interface.

DM is a Java-based Web Service (built on the 52°North WPS framework) operating on Apache Tomcat, enhanced with gCube libraries [R7]. The DM architecture consists of two server clusters within a Virtual VRE: the Master Cluster and the Workers Cluster, as shown in Figure 7. Typically, each cluster comprises 16 servers managed by a HA-Proxy load balancer, which evenly distributes requests. Every server runs a DM service, which informs the Resource Registry of its presence and capabilities. The Resource Registry indexes the load balancer, which serves as the primary interface for different DMs. The Workers Cluster is dedicated to cloud computations.

Figure 7. The DataMiner System architecture.

The Master and Workers clusters are dynamically set up by D4Science, using an orchestration engine with Ansible scripts for consistent, reliable configuration of multi-tier applications.

Upon receiving a WPS request, the Master Cluster's balancer allocates it to one of its services (master DM). These DMs host various processes from multiple developers, including both local and cloud algorithms. Local algorithms execute directly on the master DMs, making use of parallel processing and significant memory. Cloud algorithms, on the other hand, operate on distributed computing principles like MapReduce and depend on the Workers Cluster's DMs (cloud nodes).

DM enhances the standard 52°North WPS implementation with features that promote user collaboration and result repeatability and reusability. This is achieved through the integration of common services in the infrastructure. Notably, DataMiner can process inputs from workspace folders shared among users, facilitating collaborative complex experiments. Inputs can also be received via HTTP links or embedded in WPS execution requests. The computation outputs are first stored in distributed cloud storage and then returned to the client. Subsequently, a separate thread makes these results accessible in

the user's workspace. After each computation, a workspace folder is created containing inputs, outputs, parameters, and a provenance document summarising this data. This folder, shareable with others, allows for the re-execution and sharing of the entire execution process, thereby encouraging collaborative experimentation.

2.3.1.4 Analytics Engines Comparison

Table 1 compares the two different systems: Data Miner and CCP, focusing on various features relevant to their functionalities, across various technical aspects.

For virtualisation, Data Miner utilises "classic" virtual machines whereas CCP employs containers with isolated runtime. In terms of execution infrastructures, Data Miner's infrastructure is chosen by VLab management per VLab, while CCP offers multiple infrastructures selectable by users. For standard protocols, Data Miner uses OGC WPS (XML), contrasting with CCP's OGC API Processes (JSON).

The Method integration in Data Miner is handled through the SAI with GitHub support, while CCP integrates via Method Importer and supports any Code Versioning System (CVS). Data Miner excels in parallel executions, including MapReduce, whereas CCP's parallel execution support is basic but expected to improve. Regarding the availability of methods, Data Miner has many ready-to-use options, in contrast to CCP's fewer out-of-the-box methods. Both systems integrate with JupyterLab and RStudio, but CCP's integration is notably easier, also due to a code generation tool. Finally, the front-end technology of Data Miner is based on Rich Internet Applications (RIA), whereas CCP uses a web component-based approach, exportable in multiple Content Management Systems (CMS).

Table 1. Synoptic table comparing the DataMiner and CCP engines features.

Synoptic table comparing the DataMiner and CCP engines features		
Features	Data Miner	CCP
Virtualisation	Virtual Machines	Containers, isolated runtime
Execution Infrastructures	Per VLab, selectable by Vlab management.	Multiple, selectable by users
Standard Protocol	OGC WPS (XML)	OGC API Processes (JSON)
Method Integration Tool	Software Importer (SAI) GITHub support	Method Importer, Your IDE, any CVS import

Parallel executions	Yes, also Map Reduce	Basic, more support will be added
Out-of-the-Box methods availability	Many	Few
JupyterLab Rstudio integrations	Yes	Yes, Easier (code generation tool)
Front-end technology	RIA	Web component based, exportable in multiple CMS

The comparison between Data Miner and CCP reveals distinct strengths and preferences in their approach to analytics. Data Miner, with its use of classic virtual machines, excels in parallel executions and offers a wide range of ready-to-use methods, making it robust and immediately functional. Its integration through SAI and GitHub support indicates a focus on established technologies although with a learning curve that may be steeper.

On the other hand, CCP's use of containers and a web component-based front-end technology demonstrates a modern, flexible approach, allowing for a customisable user experience and easier integration with popular platforms like JupyterLab and RStudio.

Moreover, CCP's support for multiple infrastructures and a broader range of CVS, along with its potential for improvement in parallel execution capabilities, shows a system designed for adaptability and future growth. While each system has its unique advantages, the choice between Data Miner and CCP would largely depend on the specific needs of the scientific community, whether it be immediate, out-of-the-box functionality or a more customizable, modern approach.

2.3.2 JupyterHub

JupyterHub is an open-source web application that allows multiple users to access and use Jupyter notebooks within a shared computing environment. It is particularly valuable in educational and research contexts, as it simplifies the deployment and management of Jupyter notebooks for multiple users. Notebooks are increasingly recognised as the standard tool for offering an easy-to-use online coding system coupled with interactive computing. In the Blue-Cloud VRE, the establishment and management of a Notebook service that integrates with the Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs must meet several key criteria:

- The service must be seamlessly integrated and accessible through various Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs;
- It should be harmonised with the Blue-Cloud VRE Identity and Access Management Service;
- Access to the Blue-Cloud Storage services is essential, enabling users to interact with files in the V Labs directly from the Notebook environment.

- Users should have the option to select from diverse Notebook versions, differing in pre-installed software and hardware specifications.
- There should be a facility for users to publish their notebooks within the Blue-Cloud VRE catalogue

JupyterHub has been installed on the Blue-Cloud VRE Kubernetes cluster. This setup provides a robust Notebook service offering uninterrupted access from the graphical interface of the Blue-Cloud V Labs.

The reference architecture for the JupyterHub solution within the Blue-Cloud VRE is illustrated in Figure 8. The Kubernetes solution automates the provisioning of Notebook servers. These servers, functioning as containers, provide users with options to choose specific image flavours and set limitations on CPU and RAM usage for each instance. The flexibility of the Kubernetes environment allows for scalable deployment, enabling the addition of new machines (worker nodes) to the existing cluster to enhance service capacity as needed.

Figure 8. Jupyter Hub solution reference architecture.

The project Zero to JupyterHub is pivotal in deploying JupyterHub on Kubernetes. It offers a range of customizable add-ons crucial for integration within the Blue-Cloud framework. One notable feature is the extension of JupyterHub authentication system to incorporate the Blue-Cloud Identity and Access Management Service. A specialised JupyterHub Authenticator class has been developed for this purpose. This class retrieves a user's personal OpenID Connect token from a VLab and employs it to access user account details in the JupyterHub database.

JupyterHub allows users to run different server instances (which might differ in hardware specifications or pre-installed libraries) according to the user's needs. Within the Blue-Cloud VRE JupyterHub is used to spawn both JupyterLab Notebooks and RStudio applications on the selected dedicated VRE Cloud servers. Independently from the fact that

they are JupyterLab Notebooks or RStudio, Blue-Cloud offers different instances and the possibility to customise them based on the VLab requirements. These instances are similar in capacity and have ready-to-use libraries that are useful to conduct the activities of Blue-Cloud V Labs. Images are automatically built and published to a container registry (e.g., DockerHub) to make them available for the Kubernetes cluster. The system is highly flexible, so new servers can be easily allocated as needed in Blue-Cloud, in order to meet the demands and needs of the users.

Additional integration steps were undertaken to enable access to the Blue-Cloud VRE workspace. This access is established using the StorageHub Fuse library, enabling the mounting of user workspace folders within the Notebook environment. This feature is enabled by the StorageHub Fuse component, a custom component developed to work with the Linux Filesystem in Userspace (FUSE) software interface. This connects the Linux filesystem and the Blue-Cloud VRE workspace backend service, i.e., the StorageHub service. The library integration ensures that the workspace can be mounted in a sidecar container (a specific container that runs with the main container to provide extra functionality) alongside the user's primary Notebook container, and it is accessible within the user's home directory.

Furthermore, the Kubernetes cluster was configured with an NFS server to accommodate user volumes. This configuration serves the purpose of providing persistent working directories for users and supporting a persistent shared Dataspace for each VLab.

2.3.2.1 JupyterLab

JupyterLab represents the latest web-based interactive development environment catering to notebooks, code, and data. Its adaptable interface empowers users to customise and organise their workflows in fields such as data science, scientific computing, and machine learning. JupyterLab is seamlessly integrated, ensuring its smooth operation and management within a clustered environment running within the above described JupyterHub service on Kubernetes as depicted in Figure 8.

Since JupyterHub uses ephemeral storage, all the content stored in that host may be removed at the end of the session. All the data, scripts and other resources that the user needs to persist have to be stored into the Workspace or Dataspace that are accessible through JupyterLab.

2.3.2.2 RStudio

RStudio enables the execution of real-time statistical analyses using R, a programming language designed for statistical computing and graphics. RStudio is seamlessly integrated, ensuring its smooth operation and management within a clustered environment running within the above described JupyterHub service on Kubernetes as depicted in Figure 8.

All the data, scripts and other resources that the user needs to persist have to be stored into the Workspace or Dataspace that are accessible through RStudio.

2.3.3 ShinyProxy and Containerised Apps

ShinyProxy offers a robust platform for deploying Shiny applications in enterprise environments, eliminating limitations on concurrent app usage. Shiny, a comprehensive R package, simplifies the creation of interactive web applications directly from R, lately Shiny for Python language was also added. These applications can be seamlessly integrated into R Markdown documents or utilised to construct dynamic dashboards, merging R's computational capabilities with the web's interactivity.

Employing ShinyProxy for deploying a Shiny app involves encapsulating the application within an R package, followed by its integration into a Docker image. This methodology brings several significant benefits:

- Isolation and Security: Each user session is managed within a completely isolated environment, bolstering security and stability;
- Flexible Environment Management: Supports various Docker images, accommodating different R and Shiny versions;
- Resource Optimization: Memory and CPU usage can be finely tuned via the Docker API.
- Streamlined Monitoring and Debugging: utilises standard Docker tools for effective system monitoring and troubleshooting.

2.3.3.1 Blue-Cloud VRE and Containers Orchestration

In the Blue-Cloud VRE, container orchestration is a critical component, utilising both Docker Swarm and Kubernetes:

- Docker Swarm: Manages multiple Docker containers across a virtual machine cluster. Key components include a manager container orchestrating the environment and agent containers ('docker machines') that execute Docker containers. The manager employs a least-utilised algorithm for efficient container allocation.
- Kubernetes: As an additional orchestration tool, Kubernetes offers enhanced scalability and management features. It provides robust mechanisms for automated deployment, scaling, and operation of application containers across clusters of hosts, further augmenting the capabilities of Docker Swarm within the Blue-Cloud VRE.

Overall, these technologies, while catering to ShinyProxy, also effectively support the deployment of other Docker-containerised applications, showcasing their adaptability and scalability in the Blue-Cloud VRE platform.

Figure 9 provides a detailed depiction of a Docker Swarm instance actively managing multiple Docker containers distributed across a cluster of virtual machines. This setup is crucial for ensuring efficient resource allocation and high availability in distributed

computing environments. Docker Swarm employs a sophisticated management system, central to which is the manager container. This manager container operates on a designated virtual machine, tasked with the comprehensive management of the Docker environment. It is responsible for deploying containers across various agents within the cluster and continuously monitoring and reporting the status and deployment details of each container, thereby maintaining a cohesive and well-organised cluster.

Figure 9. Blue-Cloud VRE cluster supporting Shiny and any other Docker app.

The manager container is not merely a supervisory entity, it represents the primary interface for Docker operations, orchestrating the entire container lifecycle within the Swarm. Agents, functioning as 'docker machines', are critical components of this architecture. These agents, hosted on individual virtual machines, register themselves with the manager and are responsible for running the Docker containers. This registration is pivotal for the distributed nature of Docker Swarm, enabling a seamless, coordinated operation across the cluster.

When a client initiates a request to start a container, the manager's role becomes even more significant. It employs a sophisticated algorithm to locate an appropriate agent with available capacity. This algorithm, known as the least-utilised algorithm, ensures equitable distribution of workload by selecting the agent currently running the fewest number of containers to execute the newly requested container. This strategy not only optimises resource utilisation, rather it also improves the overall efficiency of the system.

Additionally, Docker Swarm's architecture requires additional capabilities for robust operation, especially in complex network environments. These include routing external

traffic into the cluster, effectively load balancing across multiple container replicas, and facilitating DNS (Domain Name System) service discovery. These functionalities are vital for ensuring that Docker containers are accessible and operate efficiently under varying load conditions. To address these needs, the Blue-Cloud VRE integrates the HAProxy load balancer. HAProxy is renowned for its high performance and reliability, making it an ideal choice for managing traffic flow, ensuring even distribution of requests across the containers, and providing essential DNS resolution services within the Docker Swarm cluster.

2.4 Storage Framework

The Storage Framework is composed of several storage technologies operated to deliver two key services: the Workspace and the Dataspace. Both of them work like a typical file system with folders that contain files and other digital items (e.g. hard and soft links), and both of them exploit tailored storage devices. Despite the similarities, the Workspace and the Dataspace are designed to own different features and deliver different capabilities that are synthetically reported in the following sections.

2.4.1 Workspace

The Workspace provides large, secure and reliable access to a storage volume that contains different spaces:

- VRE space: a shared storage area that is linked to any VLab and accessible by all VLab members;
- Shared space: a storage area that is created by a user and shared with other users;
- Private space: a storage area that is exclusive to any user. It hosts the DataMiner space, where the provenance information of each job run by the DataMiner engine is automatically stored; the VRE Data pool, where the datasets accessed through the Data Discovery & Access service are persisted; the CCP space, where the provenance information of each job run by the Cloud Computing Platform engine is stored upon request of the user.
- Volatile space: a temporary and fast space, where to store transient files that are automatically removed after a configurable period of time, set to one week for the Blue-Cloud community.

The access to shared areas is regulated by selecting one of the following access policies:

- Write Own: users can only update/delete their own files;
- Write Any: any user can update/delete any file;
- Read Only: users can read any file but cannot update/delete.

Regardless of the access policies that control the access of all other users, the VLab Manager has the authority to administer the VRE space that is linked to the VLab under their management and the owner of a shared folder can administer the folder that they choose to share.

Figure 10 depicts the Workspace solution reference architecture. From the top, the workspace service acts as the interface layer, comprising the Workspace Portlet, Widget, and REST API. These components serve as the user's entry point to the VRE, facilitating interaction through Web Graphical User Interfaces and programmatic access via an API. The Storage Hub serves as an intermediary abstracting the complexity of data storage and retrieval operations. This layer ensures a seamless integration of the data persistence mechanisms, which are represented at the bottom tier of the architecture. The data persistence layer is indeed split into two distinct storage systems: S3 (Simple Storage Service) Storage for data, persisted in an object storage for scalable and secure data storage solutions; and Graph DB (Database) for metadata, enabling efficient metadata storage, querying, and management.

Figure 10. Blue-Cloud VRE Workspace solution reference architecture.

Each workspace element, whether a folder or a file, is equipped with metadata, including a name, a description, creation and update dates, the history of actions performed by any user on that element, and the list of versions for the same file. This set of metadata can be easily extended using the APIs of the Workspace service. Additionally, every file may support a content preview automatically generated according to its content type, and it is also possible to make links (as URIs) to it. For folders, these links can enable others to access the folder in “guest mode”, without needing to log in. The contextual menu offers shortcuts for some actions on it, such as publishing the item into the catalogue, or initialising a data miner process with the item as input.

The workspace supports in an efficient way encryption, compression, replication, versioning, and persistent unique identifiers as follows:

- **Encryption:** it uses a strong encryption algorithm to protect the data from unauthorised access. The encryption keys are managed by D4Science and depending on the level of control and security required may change for each VRE or

community. Encryption is applied to data when they are persisted in the cloud and automatically decrypted when accessed via the Workspace interface or APIs;

- Compression: it reduces the size of the data by applying a compression algorithm, such as gzip, to save storage space and bandwidth. Compression is performed by D4Science to data when they are persisted in the cloud and automatically decompressed when accessed via the Workspace interface or APIs;
- Replication: it ensures the availability and durability of the data by replicating it across multiple servers and locations. The replication can be synchronous or asynchronous, depending on the consistency and latency requirements. For the Blue-Cloud VRE, synchronous replication has been selected. With synchronous replication data is written to both primary and secondary storage devices at the same time. This ensures that the data is always consistent and up-to-date on all sides. However, this also demands more network capacity and performance and can create latency and complexity. It has been selected to offer to the application's high availability and fast failover. Replication also enables disaster recovery and backup scenarios.
- Versioning: it stores multiple versions of a file in the same storage location. This feature lets the user save, access, and restore any version of a file that is stored in the service. With versioning, any user can undo accidental deletion or modification of the data. For example, if the user deletes a file, the Workspace does not erase it completely but moves it to the recycle bin where it can be easily restored. If the user overwrites a file, the Workspace makes a new version and keeps the old one assigning to each version a persistent unique identifier. Each version can be either accessed via the persistent unique identifier or restored as the default version. Versioning enables high availability, durability, and consistency for the data. However, it also consumes more storage space and network bandwidth, as each version of an object is a full copy and not just the difference from the previous version.
- Persistent Unique Identifier: it assigns a unique, web-friendly, and persistent identifier to any file and folder stored by it. This identifier does not depend on the location or the content of the object but on the metadata that is written on the Workspace. It can be used to access the object using two types of persistent URLs (PURL) associated with it by the Workspace. The first type of PURL is a link to either the file or the folder that validates the access policies associated with it by verifying the user's identity and access privileges. The second type of PURL is a link to either the file or the folder that enables anonymous access to it.

The Volatile space is configured to lack replication and versioning and to deliver low latency and faster read and write speed. The persistent unique identifiers are UUIDs that are used to access the files via the Workspace APIs.

2.4.2 Dataspace

The Dataspace provides large and secure access to a storage volume, allowing users to access and share files over a network, as if they were stored locally. It can be configured

with different access control lists (ACL) to enable either read-only mode or read-write mode according to the user role in the VRE (see Figure 11).

Unlike the workspace, the Dataspace is designed to be stateless. This means that the Dataspace does not store any information about the user's activities and therefore the history of operations performed on the file is not supported. This enables efficient and fast recovery from crashes.

The Dataspace lacks features such as encryption, compression, replication, versioning and persistent unique identifiers. However, it compensates for these limitations by providing large volumes (in the order of terabytes) with significantly faster read and write speed, lower latency, and lower congestion compared to the Workspace (see Figure 12).

Figure 11. Blue-Cloud VRE Dataspace solution reference architecture.

Figure 12. Blue-Cloud VRE Workspace vs. Dataspace; Persistent vs. Volatile storage.

2.5 VRE Management System

The VRE Management System encompasses a range of services and applications that provide functionalities for the design, creation, and deployment of Virtual Labs. V Labs are specialised VREs designed to support specific research communities. They provide a collaborative platform for researchers to access and share data, utilise scientific tools and workflows, and conduct their research projects. These services facilitate VLab Designers and VRE Managers in using graphical user interfaces to communicate the required features of a desired VLab to the Blue-Cloud infrastructure. They also allow for easy updates to the VLab once it is defined and operational.

Managing these collaborative environments involves a four-stage process:

- A definition stage where a VLab Designer outlines the features of a new VLab to support a specific application scenario;
- An approval stage where the VRE Manager decides on the feasibility of the proposed V Labs, determining whether they should be accepted or rejected. For accepted V Labs, the VRE Manager also decides on deployment details, such as the hosting nodes to be used;
- A verification stage where the VRE Manager validates the VLab as per the specifications approved earlier;
- A management stage where the VRE Manager customises certain elements of a deployed VLab (such as the layout of the user interface components, known as portlets) and monitors the overall operational status of the VRE.

For more comprehensive information, visit the gCube Wiki page dedicated to this service at https://wiki.gcube-system.org/gcube/VRE_Administration.

This system, which pre-dates the Blue-Cloud initiative, has been redesigned over time to align with evolving technologies.

3. Introduction to IRISCC

Use Cases

(Demonstrators)

In this paragraph the IRISCC Demonstrators are shortly described. For a more detailed description of the six IRISCC Demonstrators please see public IRISCC Deliverable D4.1 Report on the full Demonstrator design (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13880714>). In this deliverable you will also find all technical details reported by the Demonstrator responsible persons collecting demonstrator technical details needed to estimate efforts for integration/adaptations as a basis to define the roadmap for onboarding. This spans from Programming language, Computational Resources up to which data is used and who is the data owner. In the Table 2 we list the contact persons for the IRISCC Demonstrators.

Table 2. Contact persons for the six IRISCC Demonstrators.

Contact persons for the IRISCC Demonstrators	
Demonstrator	Contact Person (Affiliation acronym)
Demo #1	Roel Vermeulen (UU)
Demo #2	Dick Schaap (MARIS)
Demo #3	Harry Vereecken (FZJ)
Demo #4	Pablo Serret Ituarte (UVigo)
Demo #5	Karel Klem (CzechGlobe)
Demo #6	Lucia Mona (CNR)

3.1 The Risk on human health in urban areas during heatwaves associated with deteriorated air quality (DEMO #1)

This Demonstrator will provide access to air quality data (e.g., ozone, fine particles, black carbon, oxidative stress potential of particles, chemical composition) from ACTRIS and IAGOS, and health-related data (hospital-related data) from EIRENE projects for specific cities (Athens, Barcelona, Paris) during recent heat waves. It aims to showcase the ability of Research Infrastructures in Health and Environment to collaborate and facilitate access to information linking heatwaves and associated air quality impacts on human health. The target users include academics, public officials, sectors like urban planning, construction, housing, and health, as well as the general public.

Target Users:

- **Public health researchers:** Scientists studying the health impacts of air pollution and extreme weather events.
- **Government agencies:** Organisations responsible for public health, environmental protection, and urban planning.
- **Healthcare providers:** Hospitals, clinics, and health professionals working in areas affected by heatwaves and air pollution.
- **Public:** Individuals concerned about the health risks associated with heatwaves and air quality.

This Demonstrator will contribute to a better understanding of the health implications of climate change and inform the development of effective mitigation and adaptation strategies.

3.2 The Risk on coastal regions due to flooding caused by sea-level rise and storm surges (DEMO #2)

This Demonstrator will develop A Jupyter notebook to evaluate the extent and patterns of coastal flooding caused by storms and the long-term effects of sea-level rise due to

climate change. It will also assist in analysing the impacts on terrestrial ecosystems and the effectiveness of potential mitigation measures. By combining advanced hydrodynamic models with Earth Observation and in-situ data, the notebook will enable researchers to conduct flooding and impact analysis scenarios. This scalable and adaptable solution can be customised and used by researchers as target users to study various coastal regions.

Target Users:

- **Coastal scientists:** Researchers studying coastal processes, sea-level rise, and flooding impacts.
- **Environmental engineers:** Professionals working on coastal protection and adaptation measures.
- **Government agencies:** Organisations responsible for coastal management and disaster preparedness.
- **Communities:** Residents and businesses located in coastal areas who are concerned about flooding risks.

This Jupyter notebook will provide a valuable resource for understanding and addressing the challenges posed by coastal flooding, and for developing effective strategies to protect coastal communities and ecosystems.

3.3 Risk on terrestrial ecosystems functioning and services due to droughts and heatwaves (DEMO #3)

This Demonstrator will provide data from a water monitor and a seasonal-to-seasonal forecasting system to evaluate the risks of droughts and heatwaves on terrestrial ecosystem functioning and services. The products include a Mosaic Hydrological Model mHM-based European drought monitor and a Terrestrial System Modeling Platform TSMP-based ecosystem reanalysis product focusing on hydrological components like soil moisture and water use efficiency. These products are validated using data from eLTER, ICOS, and AnaEE. The target users include academics, public officials, sectors such as water management, forestry, and agriculture, as well as the general public.

Target Users:

- **Environmental scientists:** Researchers studying terrestrial ecosystems, hydrology, and climate change.
- **Government agencies:** Organisations responsible for water resource management, agriculture, and forestry.

- **Policymakers:** Individuals involved in developing and implementing climate change adaptation strategies.
- **Public:** Individuals interested in understanding the risks of droughts and heatwaves and their potential impacts on their local environment.

This Demonstrator will provide essential information for addressing the challenges posed by droughts and heatwaves and for developing effective strategies to protect terrestrial ecosystems.

3.4 Risk on marine ecosystems biodiversity, functioning and services caused by ocean acidification, warming and deoxygenation (DEMO #4)

This Demonstrator will offer a comprehensive approach to investigate the risks of ocean acidification, warming, and deoxygenation on marine ecosystems' biodiversity, functioning, and services. By combining EMBRC's marine organism and mesocosm facilities, ICOS's CO₂ uptake and release data, SeaDataNet's chemical data and upscaling tools, CCMAR's species distribution modelling projections, and eLTER's long-term ecosystem observations, this initiative will unite the expertise and resources of various Research Infrastructures. This integrated approach will enable future target users, including modellers, biologists, engineers, government agencies, and companies, to explore and develop climate change mitigation strategies.

Target Users:

- **Marine scientists:** Biologists, oceanographers, and ecologists studying marine ecosystems and their responses to climate change.
- **Modellers:** Researchers developing and using models to simulate ocean processes and predict future impacts of climate change.
- **Government agencies:** Organisations responsible for marine resource management, conservation, and policy development.
- **Industry:** Companies operating in marine sectors, such as fisheries, aquaculture, and tourism, who need to understand and adapt to changing ocean conditions.

This Demonstrator will empower researchers and stakeholders to explore the complex interactions between ocean acidification, warming, and deoxygenation, and to develop effective strategies for mitigating their negative consequences.

3.5 Risk on food security due to multi-hazard risks (pests, diseases, drought, heatwaves) (DEMO #5)

This Demonstrator will develop a comprehensive service to assess the combined effects of multiple agricultural risk factors like drought, high temperatures, and pests/diseases. It integrates individual risk evaluations (on a 5-level scale) into a single "risk semaphore" and visualises the spatial distribution of combined risk on a map. Here a risk semaphore is a visual tool used to communicate the level of risk associated with a particular situation or event. It typically uses a colour-coded system, similar to a traffic light, to quickly and easily convey the severity of the risk.

The Demonstrator leverages data from manipulation experiments (AnaEE) to understand complex interactions between risk factors, and combines it with observations from ICOS and eLTER platforms. It introduces new parameters that account for the intensity, duration, and synergistic/antagonistic effects of multiple factors on food production and quality.

Following integration with existing tools like the AgroRisk.cz portal (www.agrorisk.cz), the Demonstrator will enable predictions of environmental and biotic risk impacts on agricultural products. The portal utilises biological models to predict risks based on weather data and analyses their combined effects on yield and quality (e.g., mycotoxin contamination).

Finally, the Demonstrator incorporates data from observation platforms and remote sensing to validate forecasts, refine spatial risk distribution, and continuously improve prediction models. This ongoing feedback loop ensures the service remains relevant and accurate for its target users.

Target Users:

- **Farmers and agricultural producers:** This service will empower them to make informed decisions about their crops by providing a clear picture of potential risks.
- **Agricultural advisors and extension services:** They can use this tool to provide targeted advice and support to farmers based on the specific risks in their region.
- **Policymakers and risk management agencies:** The data can inform policy decisions related to agricultural risk mitigation and support programs.

3.6 Risk on multiple systems due to wildfires in Europe (DEMO #6)

This Demonstrator will provide data on wildfire events affecting Europe to aid in understanding their impacts. For active fires, it will offer information on the source area, affected regions, plume movement, distribution, and characteristics (including CO and aerosol content). The Demonstrator is based on near to real-time data from various Research Infrastructures (ACTRIS, IAGOS, ICOS, eLTER), transport models, and offline analysis.

Target Users:

- **Researchers:** Climate, air quality, health, carbon neutrality, and ecosystem scientists
- **Copernicus Services:** CEMS, CAMS, C3S, and EOSC
- **Socio-economic Sectors:** Air quality management, agriculture, and transportation infrastructure

This resource will be valuable for studying the effects of wildfires on climate, air quality, human health, and ecosystems, and can support decision-making in various sectors.

4 Steps to develop the Roadmap to integrate Demonstrator in the VRE

The demonstrators were planned at conceptual level and presented already in the IRISCC project proposal in March 2023, but the timeline and process for actually implementing the demonstrators started in April 2024 at the onset of the IRISCC project. The first six months of the project included more detailed planning of the demonstrators, which resulted in the initial plans as provided in IRISCC deliverable D4.1 (to be submitted).

The IRISCC project aims to achieve harmonisation and interoperability between IRISCC services. It is considered effective and productive to adopt the D4Science e-infrastructure for developing and implementing the demonstrators as planned in WP4. D4Science already provides an existing and proven interoperability framework. Therefore, for the realisation of the demonstrators, a close cooperation is planned between WP4 and WP6. This will result in IRISCC digital and analytical services that make optimal use of common resources and will operate in the production stage in the same e-infrastructure environment, which will benefit IRISCC users and also the sustainability perspective. Furthermore, having a common e-infrastructure platform for carrying, partly or fully, all demonstrators will also make it easier and more effective to arrange gateways to common data repositories, relevant for the demonstrators, such as those provided by RIs, Copernicus services (CMEMS, C3S (ERA5, ORAS5, ...)), ECMWF, and possible international climate resources. In addition, the D4Science VRE already offers smart connectivity to EOSC and other e-infrastructures, such as EGI, EUDAT which might be relevant for powering the IRISCC demonstrators.

VRE experts in IRISCC WP6 team will give support to WP4 Demonstrator teams to ensure optimal use of the D4Science resources, and to achieve a FAIR deployment for the demonstrators, which will lower the threshold for access and use by targeted IRISCC users.

D4Science features common services for federated EOSC AAI (Authentication and Authorisation Interface), accounting, monitoring, storage, computing, and provenance data management. The provenance data are associated with final results of analytical workflows, resulting in reproducible scientific findings. In this way, D4Science is ready for support of open science practices, which also will be beneficial for the WP4 demonstrators.

4.1 Proposed Initial Roadmap

Considering WP4 and WP6 activities, a timeline is proposed for going from concept and initial plan to more detailed specifications for each Demonstrator and the way in which

demonstrators can make optimal use of D4Science to the actual development and implementation.

In this paragraph we summarise the first actions taken to sketch the planned further steps going from idea to functional and technical specs and to implementation over two year period:

1. **Assessment of Demonstrator Needs:** Evaluate the specific requirements of each demonstrator in terms of data, computational resources, and collaboration tools.
2. **Integration Planning:** Develop a detailed plan for integrating selected services and data from the demonstrators into the D4Science VRE.
3. **Technical Implementation:** Implement the necessary configurations and connections to ensure seamless integration and interoperability.
4. **Testing and Validation:** Thoroughly test the integrated services to verify their functionality and performance.
5. **Documentation and Training:** Create comprehensive documentation and provide training materials to support users in accessing and utilising the integrated services.

4.2 Initial WP4–WP6 meetings at the Kick-off meeting and follow-up

During the IRISCC kick-off meeting in Helsinki and online on 5.6.2024 a first outline of the different Demonstrators has been presented as part of WP4, while as part of WP6 a first presentation was given of the D4Science VRE e-infrastructure and the aims to make use of D4Science as an interoperability framework and platform for developing, deploying, and operating (part) of the workflows and services of the planned demonstrators. Establishing this synergy requires further analyses and close interaction between the WP4 Demonstrator developers and the WP6 D4Science providers.

As a result of the workshop WP4 worked on further detailing the Demonstrators from an idea to more firm concepts, which has been documented in IRISCC Deliverable D4.1. WP6 worked on further detailing the functionalities and architecture of D4Science, using the Blue-Cloud VRE instance as a perfect example for IRISCC. Moreover, a checklist has been composed of questions which need to be discussed and answered in the coming months by and between the WP4 and WP6 developer teams. The results of WP6 are documented in IRISCC Deliverable D6.2 (this document).

4.3 Next step: a joint WP4–WP6 workshop

The Deliverables **D6.2** and **D4.1** provide input for setting-up a **joint WP4–WP6 Workshop**. This has already been fixed as a one-day online Workshop **on 18th October 2024**. The preliminary program for the Workshop will include:

- Presentation and demonstration of D4Science VRE and features.
- Hands-on exercises with D4Science.
- Presentations of planned demonstrators.
- Brainstorming about the potential synergy between each demonstrator and D4Science in order to get more firm ideas about possible integration and the level of integration.
- Brainstorming about which set of climate risk model output might be arranged by IS-ENES to support demonstrators.
- Formulating next steps.

The Workshop will bring the developers of the demonstrators and D4Science VRE closer together and this should result in better mutual understanding and more firm ideas about the proposed integration. These ideas will need to be elaborated and therefore it is proposed to give a follow-up by **6 parallel specification trajectories** (within Task 6.3) for formulating functional and technical specifications for the integration of each Demonstrator. Each trajectory involves developers from a use case and D4Science experts and dialogues will be held online over a period of 4.5 months. The resulting output will then be presented and discussed at a next **joint online Workshop on February 2025 (Month 11)** with the aim **to get a set of functional and technical specifications and a more detailed development plan by March 2025 (Month 12)**.

In the coming months, WP6 will also work on configuring and launching a version of the **D4Science VRE for IRISCC**, on which demonstrators can get an account and start their initial steps for getting more acquainted. These activities will lead to public Deliverable **D6.4 on January 2025 (Month 10)** which will report on the deployed and launched IRISCC interoperability framework with guidance documentation for service developers.

For the coming Workshop on 18 October 2024 a series of questions has been formulated in paragraph 4.4 to explore the relevance of various use cases within the context of the D4Science VRE. These questions will be discussed during the WP4–WP6 workshop to gain a deeper understanding of the potential applications and identify any necessary adaptations or expansions of the VRE in the future.

4.3.1 Questions to the Demonstrators to be used during the workshop

General:

1. What are the services you provide (group them by individual task)?
2. Which of your services you think could be integrated into a VRE
3. Is your service user interactive
4. Do you see a benefit using a VRE for your specific service/workflow

Data:

1. Are you planning to use real time / near real time / only filed data
2. How is your data stored (Database/ Filebase/ (REST-API) portal
3. How is your data accessible (REST-API, Portal, etc...)
4. How is your data delivered (which data standard format are you using)
5. What is the amount of your data to be processed
6. What programming language, APIs or software libraries does the service depend on?
7. Which analytical tools are you using (visualisation/ statistics /...)
8. Are there licence restrictions to be considered

Metadata

1. Are you using common metadata schema for you metadata
2. Do you have a common vocabulary / ontology describing your data in a machine accessible way
3. How are the metadata accessible
4. Are there licence restrictions to be considered

Requirements for D4Science

Please try to indicate which D4Science VRE (Virtual Research Environment) services you might require for your demonstrator service. For each category, choose the service(s) that are most suitable to your needs. You may also specify additional details where applicable.

Services include Cloud Storage, Databases, Data Analytics, Data Discovery & Access.

Expected number of users: [10 – 100 – 1.000 – 10.000]

1. Cloud Storage Capacity

D4Science offers robust cloud storage features, enabling users to securely store, preserve, access, and confidentially share their data from anywhere while integrating with a wide range of data analytics services.

Select the storage capacity needed for your company's data and files in the D4Science VRE.

- [10 - 100 - 1.000 - 10.000] GB
-

2. Database Services

Please select the database system your company requires for data storage and management.

- **PostgreSQL:** A powerful, open-source object-relational database system, well-suited for handling structured data, complex queries, and high-performance transactions.
 - **TimescaleDB:** A PostgreSQL extension designed for time-series data. Ideal for handling large volumes of timestamped data and providing fast analytics over time.
 - **PostGIS:** A spatial database extender for PostgreSQL that adds support for geographic objects, allowing location queries to be run in SQL. It is widely used in geographic information systems (GIS) and spatial data analytics.
 - **Virtuoso TripleStore:** A high-performance, scalable, and flexible database designed for managing and querying linked data, especially for RDF and SPARQL applications.
-

3. Data Analytics Services

Select the data analysis tools your company requires for processing and analysing datasets.

- **Cloud Computing Platform (CCP)⁵:** A distributed computing environment that allows you to run large-scale data processing, machine learning algorithms, and analytics without needing to manage physical infrastructure.
 - Per worker VCPU Cores: [4 - 8 - 16 - 32]
-

⁵ <https://ccp.cloud.d4science.org/docs/index.html>

- Per worker Memory: [4 - 8 - 16 - 32 - 64] GB

 - **JupyterLab:** An open-source web-based interactive development environment (IDE) for notebooks, code, and data. It supports interactive computing and data visualisation, allowing users to create and share documents that contain live code, equations, visualisations, and narrative text.
 - Per server VCPU Cores: [4 - 8 - 16 - 32]
 - Per server Memory: [4 - 8 - 16 - 32 - 64] GB

 - **RStudio:** An integrated development environment (IDE) for R, a programming language for statistical computing and graphics. It facilitates statistical data analysis, machine learning, and scientific research.
 - Per server VCPU Cores: [4 - 8 - 16 - 32]
 - Per server Memory: [4 - 8 - 16 - 32 - 64] GB
-

4. Data Discovery & Access

Indicate the service that will help you with research products cataloguing, searching, and accessing datasets.

- **D4Science Catalogue Service**⁶: An open-source data management system for discovering, sharing, and publishing of Research Products. Research Products are community-defined for typologies and metadata. Makes it easy to find and retrieve products, helping organisations manage and present their assets effectively. Supports moderation when publishing.

- **D4Science GeoPortal:** An open-source data management system for discovering, sharing, and publishing of Research Products with spatial and temporal dimensions. Research Products are community-defined for typologies and metadata.

- **GeoNetwork:** A catalogue application used to manage spatially referenced resources. It provides powerful search functionalities for geospatial datasets and offers web services for browsing and accessing spatial data.

⁶ <https://api.d4science.org/gcat/docs/index.html>

- **GeoServer:** An open-source server for sharing geospatial data. It supports a variety of spatial data formats and can deliver spatial data in web-friendly formats like WMS (Web Map Service) and WFS (Web Feature Service).
 - **THREDDS Data Server:** An open-source for catalogue, metadata, and data access services offering coherent access to a large collection of archived datasets. Data access is enabled by protocols including OPeNDAP, OGC WCS, OGC WMS, and HTTP.
-

5. Other Services to be Integrated

Please select any additional applications you need to integrate into the VRE for your demonstrator service.

- **ShinyProxy:** An open-source solution for deploying Shiny applications in an enterprise setting. It provides scalability, security, and Docker integration for Shiny applications.
 - **Docker image(s):** A platform that enables developers to automate the deployment of applications inside lightweight, portable containers. Docker ensures consistency across different environments, from development to production.
 - **3rd Party Application:** Specify if you require integration with any third-party applications not listed above. Please provide details of the required app.
-

Additional Notes or Comments:

Please include any additional requirements or clarifications

Conclusions

This Deliverable D6.2 demonstrates the benefits using the framework of D4Science for the IRISCC Demonstrators. It elaborates a roadmap to onboard and host the IRISCC Demonstrators. The IRISCC Project will develop and integrate a wide range of tools and resources, enabling researchers to effectively manage, analyse, and visualise climate data. The Deliverables D6.2 and D4.1 together provide input for setting-up a series of joint IRISCC WP4-WP6 Workshops, starting on 18th October 2024. Focus developing a common VRE is to significantly advance IRISCC Demonstrators by:

- Improving data accessibility and interoperability.
- Enhancing collaboration among researchers.
- Supporting the development of new research methods and tools.
- Providing a platform for sharing and disseminating research results.

Beyond the IRISCC Project the roadmap proposed by D6.2 lays the groundwork for future developments in the VRE, such as:

- Expanding the range of available tools and resources.
- Integrating additional datasets and data sources.
- Developing new functionalities to support specific research needs.
- Strengthening the VRE's role as a hub for climate change risk research collaboration linked to ENVRI HUB Next and the ENVRI Community and beyond.

Overall, D6.2 has delivered a valuable resource for the IRISCC demonstrator development. Based on the Framework of D4science. The resulting VRE will continue to evolve and expand its capabilities to meet the evolving needs of researchers and policymakers even beyond the IRISCC Project, building upon the foundation established in this deliverable.

References

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